

Chemical Synthesis and Characterization of PPy-ZnO Nanocomposite

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Abstract:

The present study chemical oxidative polymerization used to create a PPy-ZnO nanocomposite. A naturally conducting PPy-ZnO nanocomposite with 20 wt% ZnO was produced by in situ polymerization. The effective synthesis of polymer nanocomposites was confirmed by the FTIR and UV-vis spectra. The crystalline structure with distinct peaks was confirmed by the XRD analysis. It was discovered that the average particle size was 4.96 nm. ZnO has distinctive absorption band in the FTIR at approximately 491 cm^{-1} . The presence of metal oxide nanoparticles in the polymeric nanocomposite is shown by the PPy-ZnO nanocomposites sample's notable absorption tail at 221 nm. The absorption band in the nanocomposite spectra at roughly 265–274 nm, which is carried on by the π absorption of the polymer functional groups

Keywords: Polypyrrole, Oxidative polymerization, Polypyrrole ZnO nanocomposite

Introduction:

Polypyrrole (PPy) is receiving significant attention among conjugated polymers because of its high conductivity, excellent thermal and environmental stability, and simplicity of synthesis [1]. Pyrrole has been oxidized chemically and electrochemically in organic solvents and in aqueous media to produce polypyrrole [2]. Zinc oxide (ZnO), one of the transition metal oxides, received a lot of attention in the production of PPy hybrid materials due to its multiple applications in optoelectronic devices. Zinc oxide has a large band gap of 3.37 eV, a high refractive index, thermal stability, UV protection, superior transparency, and high mobility for electrons.

Zinc oxide (ZnO), one of the transition metal oxides, received a lot of attention in the production of PPy hybrid materials due to its multiple applications in optoelectronic devices. Zinc oxide has a large band gap of 3.37 eV, a high refractive index, thermal stability, UV protection, superior transparency, and high mobility for electrons [3,4] these features have been used in new PPy applications such as thin-film transistors and light-emitting diodes. Choudhary and et al prepared *in situ* Bi₂O₃ loaded PPy nanocomposite for CO₂ detection [5]. Harpale et al prepared Polypyrrole-Zinc oxide (PPy-ZnO) nanocomposite, by chemical and electrochemical routes for detection of ammonia (NH₃) gas [6]. In present work, Polypyrrole-Zinc oxide (PPy-ZnO)

nanocomposite was investigated by XRD, SEM, FTIR & UV spectroscopy.

Experimental:

Preparation of PPy-ZnO Nanocomposite:

A chemical oxidative polymerization approach was used to create the PPy-ZnO nanocomposite. The ammonium persulphate ((NH₄)₂S₂O₈) was dissolved in distilled water and stirred continuously until it formed a crystal clear solution. After adding the monomer pyrrole (70 wt%) to this

ammonium persulphate (30 wt %) aqueous solution, the polymerization process begins. During polymerization, 20 wt% zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles were introduced to the solution using an insitu technique. After polymerization, a dark black precipitate was noticed in the beaker. To remove contaminants, the obtained sample was rinsed with distilled water, filtered through cellulose nitrate filter paper, and then dried for 24 hours at 50°C in an oven.

Result and discussion:

XRD Analysis:

Figure 1: XRD pattern of PPy-ZnO nanocomposite

The XRD of the PPy-ZnO nanocomposite was obtained using the Rigaku Miniflex 600 X-ray diffractometer. Figure 1 shows the XRD pattern of a PPy-ZnO nanocomposite, which has distinct peaks indicating crystalline nature [7] and corresponds to JCPDS Card No. 4344238. The corresponding h k l values match (1 0

0), (1 1 1), (0 3 1), (2 1 -1) and (1 2 2), planes that correlates to peaks at 2θ values 14.72°, 21.24°, 23.51°, 29.37° and 31.57° respectively, revealing the crystal structure of the PPy-ZnO nanocomposite [8]. The average particle size was evaluated using XRD and determined to be 4.96 nm.

Scanning Electron Microscope Studies:

Fig2: SEM micrographs of PPy-ZnO nanocomposites

The Fig. 2 shows SEM micrographs of PPy-ZnO nanocomposites. The micrographs show full encapsulation of ZnO particles in PPy matrix and accumulation of grains with irregular morphology. The huge Concentration of particles results in

FT-IR Analysis:

compactness in morphology [9]. This uneven and irregular morphology provide large area for adsorption of gas molecule, such morphology suitable for gas sensing application and energy storage devices [10]

Figure 3: FT-IR spectra of PPy-ZnO nanocomposite

The FT-IR spectra of the PPy-ZnO nanocomposite created with the chemical polymerization technique are displayed in figure 3. The FTIR spectrum of the PPy-ZnO nanocomposite was found to be in the 400–4000 cm^{-1} range. N-H stretching vibrations are indicated by peak in PPy at 3492 cm^{-1} . The stretching vibrations of

C=C and C-C in the pyrrole ring are correlated with the band at 1557 cm^{-1} and the weak band at 1468 cm^{-1} [11–13]. Our studies reveal that PPy is present in hybrid nanocomposites and that discrete ZnO absorption bands exist at 491 cm^{-1} . This implies that ZnO is present in the PPy chain [14].

UV-VIS Spectroscopy Analysis:

Figure 4: UV-VIS spectrum of PPy-ZnO nanocomposite

Figure 4 illustrates UV-VIS absorption spectra of the PPy-ZnO nanocomposite. Due to the presence of metal oxide nanoparticles in the polymeric nanocomposite, the formed PPy-ZnO

nanocomposites sample shows a significant absorption tail at about 221 nm [15]. The production of the nanocomposites is confirmed by the ZnO characteristic peak, which is located between 348 -378 nm. It is

important to note the absorption band in the nanocomposite spectra at roughly 265–274 nm, which is carried on by the π absorption of the polymer functional groups.[16]

Conclusion:

Chemical oxidative polymerization was accepted to create the PPy-ZnO nanocomposite. The PPy-ZnO nanocomposites demonstrate, prominent peaks in the XRD pattern of PPy-ZnO nanocomposite, confirm its crystalline nature. The average particle size was determined to be 4.96 nm. The FTIR spectra have been obtained between 400 and 4000 cm^{-1} . FTIR data reveal the presence of ZnO within the PPy chain. Metal oxide nanoparticles in the hybrid nanocomposite explain prominent absorption tail in the UV-vis absorption spectra at 221 nm. The absorption band in nanocomposite spectra at about 265-274 nm is induced by the π absorption of the polymer functional groups.

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